

HELIANTHUS TUBEROSUS CULTIVATION TECHNOLOGY.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6300854>

Hamzaliyeva Madinabonu
Fergana State University.

Annotation: *This article provides information on the geographical distribution, cultivation technology and useful properties of Yernok.*

Keywords: *Yernok, Helianthus tuberosus, vitamins, protection, geographical distribution, grows, temperature, technology.*

Yernok (*Helianthus tuberosus* L.) is a perennial herbaceous plant. Homeland - North America. In seventeenth-century Europe. Distributed in Russia in the XVIII century. It is grown in Uzbekistan as a silage crop. The appearance of the stem is reminiscent of a sunflower. The underground stem is formed by 20-70 noximon (the name of the earthworm), snout-shaped and elongated pig. The root is poppy-like, penetrates the soil by 2–3 m. Height 1.2-2.5, sometimes up to 4 m. The leaves are linear, ovate, the flowers are in a basket. Pistachio fruit, 1000 pistachios weigh 7-8 g. The aboveground stem of Yernok can withstand temperatures of -6 °, underground shoots - 20 °. Can be stored in the basement - up to 45 ° without damage, grows in unsalted soils, requires nutrients. Growth period is 120-200 days. Yernok is a technical and food plant. Eat the finished food as well. Contains 2.3% retention, 0.2% oil, 17.9% nitrogen-free, 1, 1.9% nitrogen-free, 16-18% inulin, V, C protection, 22.5 retention units per 100 kg and 1, Contains 8 kg of digestible protein. From Yernok to various medicines in medicine. To grow Jerusalem artichokes, 25-50 g of tubers are planted (large ones can be planted only in spring). Planting plan: 70x70, 60x60, depth 10-15 cm. The stem dies in the middle of summer, and in autumn it is eaten by digging. If the leaves are not harvested, the root crop will be high. Productivity: 350-500 s / ha for blue mass, 200-250 s / ha for congenital. Tugana looks good under the ground, so dig it into the necessary food. Our people also call Jerusalem artichokes. American Indians call it a means of longevity. Because there are many factors that increase the overall strength of his body. The stems are leafy, glabrous, hairy, branched upwards. The leaves are large, stiff, long-banded, the leaf blade is ovoid, the edges are serrated, the stem is opposite. The flowers are gathered in a basket and placed individually. In the middle of the basket, on the edges of the tube, are fake flowers. The color of the

flowers is bright orange. This plant does not produce seeds. Geographical distribution, blooms in July-August. Homeland is mainly North America. Today, Jerusalem artichokes are grown in large areas in America, France, England, Norway, Sweden, Russia, Ukraine and Central Asia. Regular consumption of yernok can lead to salt accumulation in the organs, type 2 diabetes, gastrointestinal diseases, deficiency, atherosclerosis, stone formation in the production and reproductive tract, neurological diseases. a lot. hand comes. Our people also call Jerusalem artichokes. American Indians call it a means of longevity. Because it has many properties that increase the overall strength of the body. Regular consumption of yernok helps to prevent salt accumulation in the organs, type 2 diabetes, gastrointestinal diseases, anemia, atherosclerosis, kidney and urinary tract stones, and neurological diseases. Yernok leaves, potatoes can be used fresh or dried. 50 g of freshly harvested potatoes. If you clean it and add it to it 30 minutes before meals, 3 times a day, your blood sugar will decrease. Leaf salad is very important not only in the treatment of diabetes, but also in the treatment of hypertension and pancreatitis. Freshly picked, add 3 pieces of groundnuts to 1 liter of water and boil for 10-15 minutes like fruit juice. If you want to use dried potatoes from Yernok, take 3 tablespoons in 1-2 liters of water and boil for 1 hour. It is recommended to drink 1 l per day, warm or chilled. Such a decoction not only lowers blood sugar, but also lowers blood pressure. Improves the function of the pancreas, increases the amount of hemoglobin in the blood.

The amount of energy Topinambur

Topinambur Sources: Each 100 g, Calories (kcal) 72, Lipids 0 g, Saturated fat 0 g, Cholesterol 0 mg, Sodium 4mg, Potassium 429mg, Carbohydrates 17g, Dietary fiber 1.6 g, Proteins 2g, Vitamin C 4mg Calcium 14mg, Iron 3.4mg, Vitamin B6 0.1mg Cobalamin 0mg, Magnesium 17mg.

To grow Jerusalem artichokes, 25-50 g of tubers are planted (large ones can be planted only in spring). Planting plan: 70x70, 60x60, chuk. 10-15 cm. The stem dies in the middle of summer, and in autumn it is eaten by digging. If the leaves are not harvested, the root crop will be high. Productivity: 350-500 s / ha for blue mass, 200-250 s / ha for congenital. The end is well kept underground, so dig it and feed it as needed. Productivity: 350-500 s / ha for blue mass, 200-250 s / ha for end. The end is well preserved underground, so it is dug as needed. Diseases: root rot, necrosis. Pests: nightshades, longhorns, caterpillars.

The appearance of the product. The shape of the fruit at the tips of the underground stems is noxious. The main fruit is formed in the center of the root, and their shape resembles a different potato. The product has a slight odor and

taste. Chemical composition. It contains vitamins A, B1, B2 and C in the underground and aboveground parts. They also contain 16-18% inulin and sugar, 16 different amino acids and pectin. To be used. Yernok activates gastric and intestinal functions, increases resistance to pathogenic bacteria, viruses and pests. It is the most effective plant in the prevention and treatment of tuberculosis, osteochondrosis, kidney disease, gray pp, angina, oncological diseases. Regular use of ground pears lowers blood sugar. Immunological parameters of the blood improve and the susceptibility to infectious diseases decreases.

Conclusion:

In short, plants that grow in nature can be a cure for certain diseases. We need to make the most of it. Yernok plant is used in diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, as well as to improve digestion.

REFERENCES:

1. Kholmatov H.H, Ahmedov O.A “Pharmacognosy” Tashkent. Cholpon-2008,
2. Pratorov.O’P, Nabiyev.M.M. “Modern system of higher plants of Uzbekistan” Tashkent. “O’qituvchi”- 2007.
3. Technology and ecology of medicinal plants. Tashkent. Thought Garden 2018.

